

SPECIAL ISSUE: Spatial Transformation from a Planning Perspective

Next level? Civil society's navigation of multi-level governance in the conflict over cycling conditions in Bavaria

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Abstract

This article argues that a crucial step towards a more nuanced understanding of civil society conflicts surrounding the mobility transition is the adoption of a spatial perspective, which considers the navigation of the involved levels of governance. To this end, we propose an analytical approach based on Conflict Field Analysis, the Embedded Agency Perspective, and multi-level governance theory: a multi-level analysis of spatially embedded conflicts. The aim of this article is to conduct a qualitative case study on how civil society actors engage with the multi-level governance system in the conflict over cycling conditions in Bavaria between 2017 and 2023. We identify three modes of engagement: firstly, addressing the established governance levels according to their respective competencies; secondly, challenging the allocation of decision-making powers across governance levels; and thirdly, co-creating new governance levels.

Keywords

Civil society;
conflict; multi-level
governance; spatial
planning;
sustainable
mobility

Introduction

The mobility transition presents a complex challenge for spatial planning (Sims et al, 2014) and is marked by conflicts rooted in entrenched power structures and divergent material interests. Central disputes concern ecological sustainability, social justice, the distribution of limited resources, and the interplay between regulatory governance and individual freedoms. These conflicts are deeply spatially embedded and require a multi-dimensional analysis. Recent research (e.g., Cox, 2023; Werschmöller et al., 2024) emphasises civil society's critical role in those conflicts, understood as competitive interactions between actors with incompatible goals (Oberschall, 1978).

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This article addresses an underexplored question: How do different governance levels influence mobility transition conflicts, and how do civil society actors navigate them within a multi-level governance system? It presents novel empirical data from a qualitative case study of the conflict over cycling conditions in Bavaria, Germany, between 2017 and 2023, during which multi-level governance played a pivotal role in the conflict dynamics.

The article begins by engaging with the literature on Germany's social-ecological mobility transition and civil society's role therein. It then introduces a conceptual framework for analysing spatially embedded conflicts, incorporating Conflict Field Analysis (CFA), the Embedded Agency Perspective (EAP), and Multi-Level Governance (MLG) theory. The methodology section outlines the case study, the qualitative methods employed for data collection and analysis, including interviews, media coverage, and a broad corpus of documents. The findings identify three distinct patterns of civil society engagement with multi-level governance. The article concludes by reflecting on implications and proposing directions for future research.

State of research

Socio-ecological mobility transition in Germany

The socio-ecological mobility transition in Germany has become a focal point of academic and policy discourse, spurred by climate targets, air quality concerns, and the challenge of transforming car-centric infrastructures. There are significant gaps between political objectives and practical implementation across governance levels. In 2024, the German transport sector once again exceeded its annual greenhouse gas emission limit (Expertenrat für Klimafragen, 2025). Recent literature (e.g. Kallenbach, 2020; Mattioli et al., 2020) underscores that a comprehensive mobility transition must go beyond technological innovation and the promotion of environmental modes of transportation to encompass “the socio-economic, cultural, and spatial dynamics and constraints that underlie social normalities and individual needs” (Manderscheid, 2023, p. 35).

Civil society's role in the mobility transition

Civil society – understood as an arena where individuals act collectively through networks, associations, and community groups without profit motives or partisan goals (Edwards, 2001) – is increasingly recognised as central to mobility transitions (e.g., Henderson & Gulsrud, 2019). It amplifies local knowledge, builds alliances, supports experimentation with alternative practices, and challenges dominant transport paradigms (Allert & Reese, 2025; Aron, 2022; Frantzeskaki et al., 2016; Herberg et al., 2020). Nonetheless, Frantzeskaki et al. (2016) caution against idealising civil society. They advocate for an empirically grounded perspective that acknowledges its

dynamic, multi-layered, and context-specific roles, as well as its evolving interactions with other actors in complex governance arrangements. Longitudinal studies are deemed essential to capture changing phases of civic engagement, while more research is needed on actors' role perceptions and contextual dynamics (Frantzeskaki et al., 2016).

The role of civil society as a driver of the mobility transition is particularly evident in Germany's recent wave of cycling referenda. Since 2015, over 50 citizen-led initiatives have emerged at municipal and state levels, demanding improved cycling infrastructure and policies (Changing Cities, 2021). Primarily volunteer-driven, these campaigns demonstrate considerable expertise, commitment, and strategic capacity (von Schneidemesser et al., 2020). They exemplify what Aron (2022) calls "momentum-based organising": a hybrid model that combines community organising with mass mobilisation, short-term tactical action, and structured leadership. In Berlin, sustained activism led to the 2018 adoption of the Berlin Mobility Act, signalling new forms of collaboration between politics, public administration, and civil society (von Schneidemesser et al., 2020; Werschmöller et al., 2024). In contrast, initiatives in places like Erlangen stalled due to unfulfilled municipal commitments (ADFC Erlangen & Radentscheid Erlangen, 2022), while initiatives in the federal state of Hesse faced administrative rejection (Hessisches Ministerium für Wirtschaft, Energie, Verkehr und Wohnen, 2022). Nonetheless, a comparative study of Berlin, Hamburg, Munich, and Frankfurt¹ argues that cycling referenda have institutionalised cycling policy agendas and shifted long-term planning priorities (Werschmöller et al., 2024). While existing studies have examined relationships between civil society and formal institutions (Frantzeskaki et al., 2016; Herberg et al., 2020; Kirchner, 2023; Schwedes, 2023), the spatial embeddedness of these interactions across governance levels remains underexplored.

Civil society and multi-level governance

In the literature there is criticism that many studies on sustainability transitions focus mainly on local agency rather than considering wider multi-level governance contexts (Ehnert et al. 2018), although scalar discourses are "integral parts of political conflicts and protests" (Engels, 2021, p. 102295). Research on civil society in the context of mobility transitions may benefit from insights gained in other fields, such as environmental politics. For instance, Anshelm et al. (2018, p. 213) contend that „the potential for politicization of environmental issues lies in their ability to cross geographical, institutional and traditional political boundaries and serve as a political rallying call for very heterogeneous groups of actors". Urkidi and Walter (2011) emphasise how

¹ Werschmöller et al. (2024) selected these cities based on their status as some of Germany's largest urban centres, their implementation of cycling policies, active local grassroots movements, and robust data availability.

constructing discourses at different scales is important for the success of civil society actors. Anshelm et al. (2018) identify several strategies for scaling up civil society conflicts: through actor alliances, discourse coalitions, and juridical processes. Meanwhile, Haarstad and Fløysand (2007) explore the relationship between scale-jumping and empowerment. However, this process is not without challenges. Local-level protests are often strongly rooted in a sense of place and collective identity, and the impacts of achieved change tend to be more tangible than at higher levels of governance (Allert & Reese, 2025; Aron, 2022; Anshelm et al., 2018). In contrast to unitary political systems, cooperative federal political systems like Germany give local transition initiatives “more opportunities to shape the rules of the game” (Ehnert et al., 2018, p. 105). However, Allert & Reese (2025, p. 7) elaborate that it “can be challenging for initiatives to identify, where they can exert agency within the transport politics field with the different levels of decision-making involved. Many individuals refrain from engagement because they don’t know where to start and feel powerless vis-à-vis a complex problem”.

Analytical approach: Multi-level analysis of spatially embedded conflicts

Conflict Field Analysis

A substantial body of research on conflicts spans planning theory, political science, and sociology. In recent years, conflict has re-emerged as a central focus in planning discourse, reflecting societal shifts and transformation processes (Fienitz & Siebert, 2023; Vitale Brovarone et al., 2023). Oberschall (1978) defines social conflicts as the result of purposeful, overt, competitive behaviour among collective actors with incompatible goals, manifesting in phenomena such as protests, strikes, or riots.

This study adopts the categorisation of conflicts introduced by Bornemann and Saretzki (2018), who distinguish four types of conflicts:

- 1) Conflicts of interest, concerning the distribution of the costs and benefits associated with specific goods;
- 2) Conflicts of values, arising from normative disagreements on environmental or technological priorities (axiological contrast);
- 3) Conflicts of knowledge, regarding what constitutes truth and valid knowledge;
- 4) Conflicts of power, concerning influence over the framing and resolution of issues (Bornemann & Saretzki, 2018).

Aligned with *agonistic conflict theory*, we conceptualise conflict as an inherent and unavoidable feature of societal change, linked to the reconfiguration of power relations (Mouffe, 2013). Mouffe (2013) argues that dissensus is foundational to pluralist democracy.

This study applies the *Conflict Field Analysis* framework, as developed by Bornemann and Saretzki (2018), which structures the analysis along five interrelated dimensions:

- *Conflict context*: The spatial, temporal, societal, and material conditions from which the conflict arises, including broader societal developments and historical trajectories;
- *Conflict actors*: The individuals and collectives who identify, engage in, and shape the conflict, including (in)formal power structures and actor coalitions;
- *Conflict dynamics*: The evolution of the conflict, including phases of emergence, escalation, and potential resolution;
- *Conflict objects*: The core issues at stake, encompassing framing processes, degrees of concretisation, and the conflict type;
- *Conflict mode*: The nature of conflict's expression – whether overt or covert, peaceful or confrontational – and the forms of conflict resolutions, such as concessions or negotiated settlements.

In many socio-ecological transitions – particularly regarding mobility – conflicts are deeply spatially embedded. We thus advocate a spatial lens in conflict analysis to uncover the interplay of actors and governance levels.

Spatial embeddedness

This article adopts a relational and multi-dimensional understanding of space, grounded in the *Embedded Agency Perspective* (Augenstein et al., 2022; Bögel et al., 2022). Space is understood here as both materially constituted and symbolically constructed, shaped by historical developments and sociocultural meanings (Mölders & Levin-Keitel, 2021). A relational approach enables the analysis of space as both the setting for agency and the product of agency² (Bögel et al., 2022).

The EAP outlines four interdependent dimensions of space (Bögel et al., 2022):

- *Physical dimension*: Tangible and visible spatial elements, such as physical geography and built infrastructure.
- *Cultural dimension*: Spatial signs, symbols, and representations, including identities and historically situated narratives.

² Our understanding of agency is grounded in the framework of Critical Realism, based on the following assumptions: 1) Social structures are enduring features of society that exist independently of individual expressions of agency (Bygstad & Munkvold, 2011; Fletcher, 2017). However, these structures are not immutable; they can be reproduced or transformed through human action over time (Bygstad & Munkvold, 2011; Fletcher, 2017). 2) Agency encompasses values, meanings, and ideas, which, although shaped by social structures, are not entirely determined by them (Bygstad & Munkvold, 2011; Fletcher, 2017).

- *Actor and agency dimension*: Social practices through which space is produced, used, and contested by social actors.
- *Regulative dimension*: Relationships of ownership, power, and control, including aesthetic, legal, and normative frameworks.

This framework offers a nuanced lens for analysing the spatial effects of societal transformations, especially in interdisciplinary contexts.

Multi-level governance

This article expands the EAP to incorporate multi-level governance³. Governance is understood as “the entire framework of social control, stewardship, and regulation which exerts power over and within society” (Blackburn, 2014, p. 102). MLG refers to dispersed, vertically and horizontally interlinked policymaking involving diverse actors – including the private sector, academia, and civil society – from the local to the supranational (Ehnert et al., 2018; Stephenson, 2013). Originally developed within political science to study the European Union (Marks & Hooghe, 2004), MLG has since been widely applied in spatial planning (Zonneveld & Stead, 2024).

MLG enhances conflict analysis by highlighting:

- The regulative context in which conflicts emerge;
- Situations where the configuration of governance levels itself becomes a source of conflict;
- The positionality of actors and power dynamics across governance levels.

The role of civil society in MLG resonates with critical geography, particularly politics of scale, which stresses the socially constructed and contested nature of spatial scales (Blackburn, 2014; Engels, 2021; Smith, 1992). Towers (2000) distinguishes institutional “scales of regulation” (where issues are politically addressed) from “scales of meaning” (where issues are experienced).

In summary, the proposed analytical framework synthesises and extends existing conceptual approaches (see Figure 1). It builds on the CFA framework by Bornemann and Saretzki, enriching it through a stronger focus on spatial embeddedness, as conceptualised in the EAP. To enhance its relevance for spatial planning, it integrates the lens of MLG. While the original CFA framework already acknowledges the roles of space and governance to some extent, this article deepens these dimensions by explicitly theorising their interconnections. This

³ It is important to distinguish between MLG and Geels’ (2011) multi-level perspective (MLP), the latter being a framework for analysing socio-technical sustainability transitions across three analytical levels: the socio-technical regime, the niches, and the socio-technical landscape.

integrated framework forms the conceptual and methodological basis for the empirical case study presented in the following section.

Figure 1 – Analytical approach (own visualisation)

Case study: Conflict over cycling conditions in Bavaria (2017-2023)

Overview of the case

This article examines the conflict over cycling conditions in Bavaria, Germany between 2017 and 2023. It comprises three interconnected sub-cases: the federal state level and two rural counties⁴. The limited number of cases allows for an in-depth analysis of the perspectives of conflict actors and their positioning within the context of multi-level governance.

Bavaria, Germany's largest federal state by area and second most populous (13.4 million inhabitants), has a longstanding cultural and historical association with automobility. Despite the adoption of the Bavarian Climate Protection Act and the goal of becoming the first climate-neutral federal state, Bavaria ranks last in the Federal State Index Mobility & Environment (Allianz pro Schiene, 2020). Cycling currently accounts for only 10% of the modal split (Bayerischer Landtag, 2023). Despite longstanding dissatisfaction, a full-scale conflict has only recently emerged, fuelled by intensified civil society mobilisation.

The study focuses on the Cycling Referendum Bavaria (*Radentscheid Bayern*), a campaign advocating for a Bavarian Cycling Law with ambitious goals, including increasing the modal share

⁴ The names of the selected counties have been withheld to protect the anonymity of the interview participants.

of cycling to 25% by 2030, expanding the bicycle lane network, and promoting sustainable transportation more broadly (Radentscheid Bayern, 2022b). The 2022 referendum may be regarded as a comprehensive attempt not only to initiate changes to legal and infrastructural frameworks but also to influence cycling behaviours. Although it was halted in its early stages by the Bavarian Constitutional Court (Bayerischer Verfassungsgerichtshof, 2023), it had a considerable impact and in response, the Bavarian government passed its own Cycling Law.

This case was selected for four key reasons:

- 1) The Cycling Referendum Bavaria is among the few such initiatives in a German territorial state – i.e. a large federal state comprising both urban and rural areas, in contrast to city states where a single urban area is both the state and the state capital.
- 2) Governance levels played a decisive role in the conflict's development. Notably, the relationship between the federal state and the municipalities was a core issue. Furthermore, the referendum was halted by the Constitutional Court on the basis of legislative competence at the federal level.
- 3) The timing was particularly favourable: data collection took place while the conflict was still ongoing, enabling real-time impressions from actors. By the time of data analysis, the conflict had (temporarily) subsided, allowing for retrospective reflection.
- 4) There was particularly good access to the field, conflict actors, and extensive data sources.

A key to understanding civil society conflicts related to the mobility transition lies in adopting a spatial perspective and paying particular attention to how actors navigate the governance levels involved. The findings of the case study therefore present the conflict lines and embed the conflict's context, actors, dynamics, objects, and mode in spatial dimensions and a multi-governance perspective.

Data collection and analysis

Qualitative, semi-structured guideline interviews (Brinkmann, 2013; Flick, 2023) were conducted with 31 experts from civil society, politics, and public administration between October 2023 and April 2024. The interviewees represented a broad spectrum of roles and organisations across multiple governance levels, including activists, non-profit organisations, local/county/state administrative bodies, ministries, mayors, and members of the state parliament members.

Interview partners were selected based on a preliminary actor analysis. The selection criteria were as follows: (1) Public and/or peer recognition as relevant conflict actor; (2) A vested interest in a specific outcome of the conflict; and (3) the capacity to influence the course of the

conflict, for example through political power or control over key resources. All interviews were documented through detailed transcripts and interview reports⁵.

Given that the study reconstructs narratives and perceptions of reality held by different actors – thus engaging with epistemological questions – interviews were particularly well suited to the research objectives.

A qualitative content analysis, more precisely a qualitatively oriented, category-based text analysis, was undertaken in line with the procedures outlined by Mayring (2022). The analysis employed the structuring technique, which aims “to filter out particular aspects of the material, to give a cross-section through the material according to pre-determined ordering criteria, or to assess the material according to certain criteria” (Mayring, 2022, p. 74). To support clarity and efficiency, the content analysis was conducted using QCAmap, a dedicated software tool.

In addition, a corpus of key documents was subjected to both quantitative and qualitative analysis (Bowen, 2009; Yin, 2017). Eighty documents⁶ from the Bavarian State Parliament were analysed based on the keywords “cycling”, “bike (bicycle)”, or “cycling law”. These documents, dated from 2017 to 2023, were assessed in terms of temporal distribution, authoring parties, and central themes.

A complementary set of documents from the same period was also analysed qualitatively, including:

- Parliamentary materials (bill readings, plenary resolutions, committee minutes, reports, and recommendations);
- Legal texts (legislation, regulations, court rulings);
- Policy documents (government and ministerial programmes);
- Political content (election manifestos); and
- Civil society publications.

Moreover, media coverage from 2017 to 2023 was analysed both quantitatively and qualitatively as it is an important factor in which levels of governance are considered by the public to be relevant as scales of meaning or regulation. This analysis focused on three newspapers: the *Süddeutsche Zeitung*, a Bavaria-based, supra-regional daily, with only Bavaria-related articles included in the sample; and the most widely circulated local newspapers in each

⁵ In the following, direct quotations from the interviews will be cited as follows: Interview number: Institution of interview partner, year of interview. The interviews were conducted in German. The direct quotes in this article have been translated by the authors.

⁶ The following types of parliamentary documents were included: written inquiries, plenary inquiries, plenary minutes of topical debates, (urgent) motions, proposed amendments, and interpellations. It should be noted that minutes from deliberation phases, plenary resolutions, committee recommendations, and committee reports were *not* included in the analysis.

of the two counties under investigation. The media selection encompassed both left-liberal and conservative perspectives. A total of 933 articles containing the keywords “bicycle traffic”, “cycling law” and/or “cycling referendum” were analysed.

Conflict context: Civil society and direct democracy in Bavaria

One crucial aspect of the conflict context lies in examining how the *regulative spatial dimension* is configured and how it interacts with the *actor and agency dimension of space*: Bavaria has attracted international criticism for its forceful suppression of climate activism. In 2024, the United Nations Special Rapporteur on Environmental Defenders under the Aarhus Convention cited Bavaria as an example of poor legislative practice concerning the right to protest. Notably, he referred to the Bavarian Police Act, which permits courts to impose preventive detention for up to 30 days – renewable once for 30 additional days –, without the individual being suspected or accused of a specific crime (Forst, 2024). This legislation was employed in 2022 and 2023 against numerous peaceful climate activists from Last Generation to prevent them from participating in further protests (Forst, 2024). The Special Rapporteur concluded that the repression of peaceful environmental activists constitutes “a major threat to democracy and human rights” in Europe (Forst, 2024, p. 2). From the perspective of those affected, such measures represent “quite simply an obstacle in the fight for the mobility transition” (Interview 28: Mobility Transition Camp Munich, 2024). In a recent case, the Free State of Bavaria refused to appoint a successful former student to become a public school teacher due to her involvement in climate and anti-car activism (Steinke, 2025).

Despite this repressive context, Bavaria has a strong tradition of direct democracy at the municipal level. Since municipal referenda were introduced into the Bavarian constitution in 1995, around 130 such procedures have taken place – more than in any other German federal state (Interview 06: More Democracy Bavaria, 2023; Mehr Demokratie e.V. Landesbüro Bayern, 2023). By contrast, referenda at the state level are comparatively rare: statistically, fewer than three petitions for referenda are initiated every ten years, with fewer than one resulting in a referendum on a draft law (Mehr Demokratie e.V., 2022). Between 2012 and 2021, for example, there was no referendum at all at Free State level (Mehr Demokratie e.V. 2022). If sufficient signatures are collected in the initial phase, citizens vote on the proposed law (and often on a counterproposal from the state parliament) within a 14-day period (Mehr Demokratie e.V., 2022). The official success rate of referenda in Bavaria stands at only 22.5 %, compared to a national average of 27.7 % (Mehr Demokratie e.V., 2022). Nonetheless, plebiscites are widely perceived as an

“instrument for initiating changes for which majorities in the population, but not in parliament, were likely. Even if the original initiators usually had to accept cutbacks to their intentions, the parliamentary compromises had a considerable modernising effect that would hardly have been achieved without plebiscitary impetus.” (Oberreuter, 2021, p. 477, own translation)

Conflict actors: Who’s involved in Bavaria’s cycling politics?

The analysis of the actor⁷ landscape in Bavaria’s cycling politics – framed through the actor and agency dimension of space – reveals the inherent complexity of a federally structured, multi-level governance system. Various actors operate at different levels – federal, federal state, county, and municipality – each representing divergent positions and interests. Responsibilities and funding for cycling infrastructure are distributed across these levels.

Federally organised political-administrative levels

International/European level: The overarching framework for climate policy in Germany, and thus indirectly for cycling policy, is shaped by international and European obligations, notably the Sustainable Development Goals and the legally binding Paris Agreement, which aims to limit global warming to 1.5° Celsius or at least well below 2° Celsius (United Nations, 2015). Relevant European Union (EU) directives include those on environmental noise (2002/49/EC) and air quality (2008/50/EC), while a recent milestone is the European Declaration on Cycling (European Parliament et al., 2024). Even if the EU level does not play a major role in the multi-level governance landscape in this field, there are various funding programmes for cycling, for example through the European Regional Development Fund and the Cohesion Fund.

National level: The legal and political parameters for cycling are largely defined at the national level – most prominently through the Road Traffic Act and the National Cycling Plan, which publicly supports the vision of Germany as a cycling nation and highlights governance and building structures across administrative boundaries as key issues (BMVI, 2021). The Federal Transport Ministry is responsible for planning bicycle lanes along federal roads and providing financial support for municipal cycling projects. The National Cycling Plan aims to further expand the scope for action of both the federal states and the local authorities and give them more flexibility (BMVI, 2021).

Federal state level: Federal states, including Bavaria, interpret and implement national regulations through their own programmes (e.g., the “Cycling Campaign” under the Climate

⁷ Following Burandt et al. (2015), we use the terms “actors” and “stakeholders” interchangeably, referring to collectives that have an interest in the outcome of the conflict and may have resources to influence the conflict process (such as power, knowledge, and legitimacy).

State Bavaria initiative). The dominant political party in Bavaria is the conservative Christian Social Union (CSU), which governed alone until 2008 and held the Federal Ministry of Transport from 2009 to 2021. In 2021, the Bavarian Transport Minister at the time commented on the new federal government: “Since the new federal cabinet does not include a single representative from Bavaria, we must keep a close eye on the interests of the citizens of Bavaria from Munich. [...] I sincerely hope that the fact that there is no longer a voice from Bavaria in the new cabinet will not take its revenge” (Staatsministerium für Wohnen, Bau und Verkehr, 2021; own translation). Currently, the CSU governs at state level in coalition with the conservative FREE VOTERS.

Party positions on cycling policy often diverge across governance levels. In a notable case, the CSU county branch in Dachau successfully passed a resolution at a party conference in 2019 urging the CSU state parliamentary faction to draft a Bavarian Cycling Law (CSU-Landesleitung, 2019). Politically, the CSU and FREE VOTERS are opposed to ALLIANCE 90/THE GREENS, the second-largest opposition party after the far-right Alternative for Germany (AfD). THE GREENS brought in more bicycle-related issues into the Bavarian state parliament than any other faction during the study period (see Figure 2) and maintain strong ties with the Cycling Referendum Bavaria Alliance (CRBA). This is also reflected in the media coverage, in which the GREENS are portrayed as very bicycle-friendly.

Figure 2 – Share of bicycle-related motions, inquiries etc. in the Bavarian State Parliament by parliamentary group (2017-2023) (own visualisation)

Authorship of cycling-related motions, inquiries etc. in the Bavarian State Parliament (2017-2023)

The Bavarian State Ministry of Housing, Building and Transport is responsible for cycle infrastructure on state roads and, in some cases on federal and county roads (when acting on behalf of the federal government or counties). From 2017 to 2023, five different CSU transport ministers held office, a situation that the Working Group of Bicycle-Friendly Municipalities (AGFK) claims slowed implementation due to recurring transition phases. In 2024, the Central Cycling Office was introduced to support the local governments. Infrastructure is physically implemented by 22 state building authorities, each responsible for several counties. This distribution of responsibilities creates a degree of municipal dependence on these authorities, and cooperation varies – ranging from constructive to strained – depending on personnel and negotiation flexibility. Coordination is often facilitated through interpersonal relationships and site visits between administrative levels.

Regional level: To a certain extent, there are also relevant activities at regional level spanning several municipalities or counties, such as regional mobility studies, joint projects and cycling concepts.

County level: Counties are responsible for funding and constructing bicycle lanes on county roads and can support municipalities in developing cycling infrastructure. While they lack formal authority to enforce integrated cycling networks, counties can play a coordinating and motivating role – by joining the AGFK or launching local funding schemes. In the process of developing the Bavarian bicycle lane network, counties made efforts to integrate municipal input to ensure bottom-up planning.

Municipal level: With over 2,000 Bavarian municipalities, the local level is widely regarded as the most critical for promoting cycling. Under Article 28 of the German Constitution, municipalities have the right to self-govern and regulate local matters autonomously. From around 2019, the federalism reform led to a trend in Bavaria towards de-bureaucratisation, deregulation and a greater transfer of responsibility for spatial planning to the municipalities (Miosga, 2022). Nevertheless, local authorities often come up against the limits of federal laws and state regulations, as is also explicitly stated in media reports. Municipal responsibilities include the planning of bicycle lanes on municipal roads, and in certain cases – depending on population size or capacity constraints at other governance levels – also on federal, district, or county roads. Many municipalities, however, struggle to prioritise cycling due to financial and staffing constraints, especially as cycling infrastructure is not a mandatory task (Bayerischer Landtag, 2021; BMVI, 2021).

Difficulties between the levels are also portrayed in the media coverage, which contributes to public awareness of the conflict conditions. These include, for example, the complex legal framework, power asymmetries in the governance structure, different points of view at different

political and administrative levels, and inter-municipal cooperation across administrative boundaries. The AGFK Bavaria plays a vital mediating role in this fragmented landscape. Founded through a municipal initiative and supported by the state, the AGFK now connects over 130 municipalities and counties committed to advancing cycling. It enables stakeholders from politics and administration to network across different levels, exchange knowledge, and learn from each other (see Figure 3) – an opportunity particularly valued by municipalities that often lack other forums for such engagement (e.g., Interview 13: County administration, 2023). The AGFK represents the interests of its member municipalities and counties vis-à-vis state and federal politicians. At the same time, the AGFK is politically influenced by the composition of the board of directors consisting of county councillors and mayors, particularly by the CSU, which has an influence on its demands and positions.

Overall, only a minority of Bavarians consider politics across various levels of governance to be cycle-friendly, with municipalities scoring slightly better (22%) than the federal state (18%) or the federal government (17%) (SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH, 2023).

The Cycling Referendum Bavaria

In early 2022, local cycling referendum initiatives joined forces to form the CRBA. Given their limited resources and organisational capacity, civil society groups such as the German Cyclists' Association (ADFC) and the German Transport Club (VCD) took leadership roles at the state level. The alliance aimed to involve “big players” (Interview 26: CRBA, 2024;) with large memberships to reach the “centre of society” (Interview 02: CRBA, 2023) through a non-partisan vibe. Key partners included environmental non-governmental organisations such as the League for Nature Conservation and political parties including ALLIANCE 90/THE GREENS, the Social Democratic Party (SPD), the Ecological Democratic Party, THE LEFT, and Volt.

The alliance also received support from a broad network of parties, civil society organisations, and youth organisations and engaged in strategic exchanges with cycling referenda in other states such as North Rhine-Westphalia and Hesse. According to interviewees (e.g., Interview 03: ADFC, 2023), the CRBA developed an internal multi-level structure: a central team at the state level managed strategy and communications, while each county had a team of spokespersons coordinating efforts with municipal actors. Counties with fewer capacities were supported through this internal network. At federal level, the various cycling referenda initiatives have joined forces to form the #Bundesrad alliance, which addresses its demands in particular to state and federal politicians. Wherever possible, the CRBA has also included international or European action days in its campaign, such as the World Bicycle Day introduced by the United Nations or the European Mobility Week.

Despite their opposition to government, the CRBA maintained a pragmatic and open approach to coalition-building. Informal discussions were even held with more market-liberal parties such as the Free Democratic Party (FDP). In contrast, links to more radical left-wing or anti-capitalist movement actors — such as Last Generation, Extinction Rebellion, or the Mobility Transition Camp Munich – remained limited. While joint participation in demonstrations and overlapping memberships occurred, formal alliances with these groups were deliberately avoided.

In the media coverage, the Cycling Referendum and other civil society initiatives for a mobility transition were predominantly portrayed very positively and their demands were given a lot of space. Representatives of civil society organisations such as the ADFC were regularly interviewed, consulted as experts, and newspaper articles were based on their data analyses. Activities such as bicycle demonstrations for the Cycling Referendum were regularly announced in advance in the newspapers analysed, which led to a wider public reach beyond the usual activists.

Figure 3 – Main conflict actors (own visualisation)

Conflict dynamics: How did the Cycling Referendum and its inherent conflicts play out over time?

The evolution of the conflict can be broadly divided into three phases.

1. Lead-up phase (2017-2020):

This initial phase was marked by widespread dissatisfaction with local cycling conditions, reflected in various grassroots initiatives calling for improvements at the municipal level. At the state level, informal lobbying efforts for a Bavarian Cycling Law and sporadic activist interventions began to emerge.

Although there tends to be more media coverage of cycling policies around elections (for example in reports on party manifestos and candidate profiles), prior to the 2018 Bavarian state elections, cycling remained a peripheral issue in mainstream political discourse. A modest rise in parliamentary interest was already observable through an increase in cycling-related inquiries submitted by parties, though (see Figure 4). The onset of the COVID-19 pandemic played a catalytic role in raising awareness of cycling, with a significant rise in usage. Several cities introduced temporary “pop-up” bicycle lanes, signalling experimental shifts in urban mobility planning.

Figure 4 – Number of cycling-related motions, inquiries etc. in the Bavarian State Parliament and cycling-related press releases of the Bavarian State Ministry of Housing, Building, and Transport per year (2017-2023) (own visualisation)

Figure 5 – Number of cycling-related articles in three selected supra-regional/local newspapers (2017-2023) (own visualisation)

2. Peak phase (2021-2023):

The conflict reached its peak between 2021 and 2023. A key turning point was a parliamentary hearing involving expert input from civil society, which significantly amplified political attention to the issue. In response, two opposition parties introduced draft legislation aligned with civil society's demands. In early 2022, the formation of the CRBA brought a new level of strategic coordination across governance levels. This collective actor succeeded in unifying diverse stakeholders and applying sustained pressure on the government while mobilising public support. The initiative rapidly gained momentum, collecting many more signatures than needed in its first phase. Compared to other Cycling Referenda in Germany, which peaked in 2020 with a sharp drop afterwards, the Bavarian peak took place rather late. This surge in civic mobilisation coincided with an explosion of media interest: in 2022 and 2023, the selected newspapers published nearly 19 times more articles on cycling-related issues compared to 2017 (see Figure 5). These articles also demonstrated a broader thematic scope: While conflicts over bicycle lanes and the distribution of traffic space have received media attention from the outset, over the years the focus has increasingly expanded to issues such as commercial bicycle traffic, relevant legislation, and road safety. Simultaneously, the Bavarian State Ministry of Housing, Building, and Transport markedly increased the frequency of its press communications on the subject (see Figure 4).

3. *Petering out (from 2023):*

The conflict began to subside in 2023 following the Bavarian Constitutional Court's decision in June to halt the referendum, and the state government's subsequent enactment of its own Cycling Law. While civil society actors regard this as a partial victory, they express clear dissatisfaction with the final outcome. One CRBA representative summarised the sentiment as: "A little bit is happening, but [...] far too little by our standards. And far too slowly, but at least something is happening." (Interview 26: CRBA, 2024) In the words of ALLIANCE 90/THE GREENS: "Your draft law is not a fancy e-bike. It's more like a walking bike with training wheels." (Bayerischer Landtag, 2023; own translation) Since then, the CRBA as a coordinated actor has receded from the political spotlight, and its members have shifted towards engagement in other platforms, such as the Alliance for a Socially Responsible Mobility Transition in Bavaria. While the conflict is not entirely resolved, it no longer occupies a central role in the political discourse. In the run-up to the 2023 state elections, federal-level issues overshadowed cycling policy despite the CRBA's efforts to keep the topic on the agenda (e.g., through a panel discussion). Nonetheless, a lasting impact is evident. According to perceptions shared by conflict actors, cycling is now more firmly embedded in the public consciousness than it was in 2017. Supporting this, 43% of Bavarians believe their local authority is more committed to improving cycling infrastructure than in previous years (SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH, 2023).

Conflict objects: What are the central positions in this conflict?

Based on a deductive-inductive analysis, several core positions in the conflict over bicycle mobility in Bavaria have been identified. Given the complexity of the issues, the following section presents a selection of particularly influential positions and examines their spatial embeddedness⁸. It is important to highlight the divergences between these positions, as public discourse – particularly within politics and public administration – frequently implies a consensus that everyone wants to strengthen cycling mobility. This obscures fundamental differences in the framing of both problems and solutions. In our analysis, we gradually uncover different layers of the conflict objects in order to get to the actual core of the conflict. Initially, aspects of conflict in the actor-related space (such as anger about perceived inconsiderate behaviour in traffic between car drivers and cyclists) and in the cultural space (for example, narratives surrounding a symbolic culture war between big cars and cargo bikes) come to the surface. According to our analysis, there are tangible material conflicts behind this, for example

⁸ Further conflict lines surround questions about budgeting, cultural aspects of automobility, differences between urban and rural areas, and more.

over the distribution of the scarce resource of space (Positions 1 and 2). If we analyse this in more depth, it becomes clear that the core of the conflict centres on questions of governance: who determines what, at what levels, and in what way? (Positions 3 and 4)

Position 1: Redistributing transport space in favour of cycling

This position demands a significant redistribution of physical transport space – such as road lanes and car parks – in favour of cycling infrastructure, including wide and high-quality bike lanes and secure bicycle parking. Proponents argue that a fair allocation of road space is essential for a successful mobility transition. As one stakeholder put it, “the major conflict [...] is: whose street is it?” (Interview 24: Bavarian Academy for Rural Areas, 2024). The spatial emphasis lies in reallocating existing transport infrastructure at the expense of car traffic.

Even though, according to the CSU, no other federal state is building as many bicycle lanes as Bavaria (Bayerischer Landtag, 2020), Bavaria is only in seventh place nationwide in terms of the total length of existing bicycle lanes, according to the Federal Ministry of Transport (Bundesministerium für Digitales und Verkehr, 2025). According to critics, the existing bicycle lanes often do not comply with current regulations and are, for example, too narrow (Bayerischer Landtag, 2021). Surveys show that the most important cycling-related demand of Bavarians is improved intersection safety and clarity, with 59% supporting increased government spending on bicycle lanes (SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH, 2023). Advocates point to the catalytic effect of infrastructure improvements on behavioural change, road safety, environmental outcomes, and a higher quality of life in urban areas. According to a Fraunhofer study, cycling has the potential to achieve an average share of 45% on all routes up to 30 kilometres if comprehensive political measures are implemented in Germany to become a bicycle-friendly country (e.g. the construction of a continuous and dense network of cycle paths) (Doll et al. 2024). There is also a network effect: high-quality infrastructure in one area creates spillover pressure on neighbouring municipalities.

Despite recent progress – including the ongoing development of a statewide cycle path concept and plans to build 1,500 km of new lanes by 2030 – stakeholders view the current approach as inadequate. With a yearly expansion rate of merely 91 metres per municipality, full coverage across federal, state, and county roads would not be achieved until the year 2160 (Radentscheid Bayern, 2023a). Achieving spatial justice would require bolder interventions: converting car parks, narrowing streets, and creating car-free urban zones. The CRBA advocated for prioritising active modes of transport in specific neighbourhoods, implementing bicycle streets free of through-car traffic, and significantly reducing motorised transport in city centres.

As one activist stated, “the car system represents an outdated, conservative worldview [...] that many white, old men still cling to” (Interview 28: Mobility Transition Camp Munich, 2024).

Position 2: Emphasising mutual consideration over infrastructure expansion

This counter-position also addresses the contested physical space but places greater emphasis on the agency and behavioural aspects of spatial interaction. Advocates reject large-scale reallocation of car space, arguing instead for “mutual consideration” among road users. The Bavarian government, for instance, defends the “principle of free choice of transport” and remains sceptical about restricting car use (Interview 17: Bavarian State Ministry for Housing, Building and Transport, 2023). Public opinion largely aligns with this view, seeing traffic areas for automobility as a “sacred cow” (Bayerischer Landtag, 2021, p. 9; own translation): 71% of Bavarians oppose converting car parking into public bicycle parking, and 64% are against converting them into cycle lanes (SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH, 2023). An author who was called in as an expert by the state parliament argued in the hearing: “The mistake of the 1960s and 1970s with the concept of the car-friendly city should not be repeated in the sense of a bicycle-friendly city. A city should be people-friendly.” (Bayerischer Landtag, 2021, p. 12; own translation)

Common concerns include traffic flow, parking availability/increased parking pressure in other areas, a loss of comfort, retail sales, access to services, and expected low usage of cycling infrastructure in some regions. Spatial constraints — such as historic city layouts or topographic barriers — also complicate expansion plans. Financial considerations weigh heavily: “I have to generate the greatest possible effect with the capital I invest,” remarked a parliamentarian from the FREE VOTERS (Interview 11, 2023).

Reflecting this attitude, the Bavarian Prime Minister has stated, “Bavaria is a car state and will remain a car state” (Bayerische Staatsregierung, 2021, p. 19). The pragmatic, incremental approach promoted by the CSU and FREE VOTERS includes relaxed standards for state-funded cycle lanes and a preference for behavioural solutions over legal mandates. As one mayor explained: “We have to show mutual consideration for each other. I don’t think we can solve everything with infrastructure” (Interview 09: FREE VOTERS mayor, 2023). Nevertheless, inconsiderate behaviour remains a core issue. While 82% of Bavarians claim to always obey traffic rules, a majority perceive others as behaving recklessly—especially car drivers failing to maintain safe distances from cyclists (SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH, 2023).

Position 3: Advocating for a strong, comprehensive cycling law

This position centres on conflicts over the regulative space, arguing that robust legal frameworks are necessary to facilitate structural change. Since 2017, organisations such as the ADFC have advocated for a dedicated Bavarian Cycling Law, supported by opposition parties such as ALLIANCE 90/THE GREENS and the SPD (Bayern SPD, 2018; Bündnis 90/Die Grünen Landesverband Bayern, 2018). Also, the Bavarian Association of Cities and Towns sees a cycling law as an important instrument and criticises the state government's version as “very vague and hesitant” and “unambitious” compared to the draft of the Cycling Referendum (Bayerischer Städtetag, 2023, p. 5; own translation).

The CRBA's draft law outlined far-reaching goals related to enhanced road safety, reduced emissions, and greater modal choice. However, the proposal was significantly reduced for legal and political feasibility. Lawyers advised a more “legally secure” text, stripped of its more ambitious demands, resulting in a version containing just a third of the original provisions (Interview 02: CRBA, 2023). The draft law's vague language, a strategic concession, was meant to ensure its passage during formal review. Even though the referendum proposed a law focussing for formal reasons on cycling, it was intended as a module of a desired future Bavarian Mobility Act (Radentscheid Bayern, 2022a).

Both the argument in favour of a comprehensive cycling law and the argument in favour of less comprehensive regulations relate to the configuration of multi-level governance. For example, media coverage reports the argument that a comprehensive Bavarian Cycling Law is needed so that it is no longer up to the municipalities themselves to decide whether and how to promote cycling in a “patchwork of competences”. In addition, certain projects such as bicycle speedways should be planned directly by the Free State and municipalities should be supported by such a law, especially in cross-municipal planning.

Parallel to the discussion about a Bavarian Cycling Law, a campaign for a Federal Mobility Act took place around 2022, for which the VCD, together with experts from civil society, academia and the mobility industry, presented a legislative proposal for mobility planning at federal, state and local level (Hermes, Kramer, & Weiß, 2022).

Position 4: Promoting voluntary incentives over legal mandates

Until approximately 2019, the governing CSU strongly opposed the idea of a Cycling Law, arguing that the Bavarian Cycling Programme 2025 — launched in 2018 with the goal of raising the modal share of cycling to 20% — was sufficient (Bayerisches Staatsministerium für Wohnen, Bau und Verkehr, 2018). Additional initiatives such as increased funding and the Climate State Bavaria campaign further underscored this voluntary approach.

Legislative proposals from the SPD and ALLIANCE 90/THE GREENS were dismissed as “unfeasible”, “unsuitable for Bavaria” (Interview 16: CSU Member of Parliament, 2023;), and even “bureaucratic madness” (Interview 11: FREE VOTERS MP, 2023). The CSU insisted on “offering options instead of imposing obligations” and rejected the use of prohibitive legislation as a tool for social transformation (Bayerische Staatsregierung, 2021, p. 11).

Ultimately, the Bavarian Cycling Law introduced by the government was designed primarily as a framework law that harmonised and codified existing funding mechanisms. Rather than introducing stringent mandates, the legislation focused on offering incentives and increasing administrative transparency. Supporting legislative adjustments included amendments to the Bavarian Road Act (2022), the Municipal Transport Improvement Subsidy Act (2023), and the Bavarian Financial Equalisation Act (2024).

Conflict modes: How do civil society actors engage within the conflict?

In the analysis of conflict dynamics, collective agency emerges as a key factor—referring not to individual actions, but to “the actions of a group of actors” (Bögel et al., 2022, p. 172). From the empirical material, three inductively derived, non-mutually exclusive modes of how civil society actors engage with the MLG system have been identified. These modes illustrate how collective agency is exercised not only within, but also on the structures of governance themselves.

Playing by the rules: Navigating the existing governance system

This mode describes civil society actors aligning their strategies with the competencies of established governance levels – local, state, and federal – thereby working within the institutional rules of the MLG system. It includes targeting relevant decision-making authorities, often simultaneously across multiple levels, and leveraging synergies between campaigns. Which level is most promising depends on the specific topic and the planning and policy instruments addressed. As also noted in other cases, the complexities of governance often present an obstacle for citizens to get involved in mobility issues – “the high number of officials who need to be addressed and the complexity of the decision-making process makes taking action a long and complicated ordeal” (Flipo et al., 2023; p. 140). In the case analysed, it is noticeable that the media coverage has made a significant contribution to shaping public perception of the governance levels at which the conflict evolution can be perceived and the levels at which the conflict can be regulated. Civil society framing is also picked up on here, for example when local activists use quotes from the United Nations Secretary-General on banners. While the analysed newspapers have reported extensively on mobility conflicts at federal and municipal level for a

long time, there was little coverage of the state level – until the mobilisation of the Bavarian Cycling Referendum changed this in the reporting.

A prime example of this first civil society approach is the evolution from local citizen petitions to the statewide Cycling Referendum. Civil society actors, upon recognising the limited street-level outcomes of their local successes, escalated their efforts to the state level. As a representative of More Democracy Bavaria observed: “That's something I hadn't seen before. That many smaller citizens' petitions were turned into one big referendum [...]. And that is why this process was very, very interesting” (Interview 06: More Democracy Bavaria, 2023). This approach requires substantial knowledge of the MLG system⁹, often acquired through informal learning processes and inter-regional networking.

The case study highlights several mechanisms of capacity-building: At the local level, civil society actors take on political roles in municipal councils or work closely with politicians and administrators in *jour fixe* format. At the state level, there has been a noticeable professionalisation of civil society (e.g., full-time coordinators, financial resources through alliance partners with a strong membership, the involvement of external expertise such as a law firm). The recognition of this professionalisation also gives actors like the ADFC access to formats in which different governance levels come together, such as the former Round Table on Cycling (since 2024, Cycling Alliance). If the internal structure of civil society organisations corresponds to the main levels of government, it is easier for them to address these simultaneously through different campaigns (as in the case of the campaign for a Federal Mobility Law, which runs in parallel with struggles at other levels). Where such structures do not exist at all levels, support from other levels can help to establish them, for example, by facilitating contacts or raising awareness for a county through events organised there by state chapters of civil society actors. Such strategic alignment is facilitated when the governance system is transparent, when multi-level strategies are well-articulated, and when political actors are open to engagement. However, it can be undermined by institutional deflection, where responsibilities are shifted between levels (the “ping-pong effect”), or by closed political attitudes – as in the refusal to involve civil society in drafting the state Cycling Law.

The approach also faces legal-structural limits. The Bavarian Constitutional Court’s rejection of the CRBA’s referendum proposal, on the grounds that certain elements exceeded state-level competence, shocked activists (Bayerischer Verfassungsgerichtshof, 2023). Notably,

⁹ For example, when drafting the Cycling Law, it was crucial to strictly adhere to the principle of connectivity (Art. 104 of the German Constitution), according to which the political level responsible for a task must also finance it (“whoever orders, pays”). If the Free State of Bavaria were to transfer new tasks to the local authorities, it would therefore have to provide the full budget for them. As the Bavarian Constitutional Court has so far interpreted the Bavarian Constitution in such a way that referenda may not cover financial aspects, great caution was required here.

similar provisions had been accepted in Berlin and North Rhine-Westphalia: “Like almost all petitions for a referendum that have been submitted to the Bavarian Constitutional Court to date, our petition for a referendum was not permitted.” (Radentscheid Bayern, 2023b; own translation) More Democracy expressed concern that this ruling might deter future direct democratic initiatives.

Still, civil society efforts persisted, albeit under different banners and in continued support of national-level campaigns such as the reform of the federal Road Traffic Act: “We still need [...] continued pressure from civil society at all levels – municipal, county, state and federal – for climate protection, the reduction of exhaust fumes and noise emissions as well as liveable cities!” (Radentscheid Bayern, 2023c; own translation)

Adjusting the rules: Contesting competence allocation

This mode involves challenging and renegotiating the distribution of authority across governance levels. The allocation of decision-making power is not static but shaped by ongoing political and societal processes. A clear example is More Democracy’s renewed call for the introduction of federal referenda. Citing the rejection of the Bavarian Cycling Referendum as evidence of state-level limitations, they advocate: “If we apparently can’t regulate this in Bavaria but on the federal level, then we need a federal referendum.” (Interview 06: More Democracy Bavaria, 2023) This demand remains controversial among political parties but reflects an attempt to reconfigure the legal architecture of participation and influence.

A related case concerns speed limits — a major issue in the cycling conflict, with many actors seeing 30 kilometres/hour zones as critical for safety. Historically regulated at the federal level, municipalities long demanded more autonomy (AGFK Bayern, 2018; Bayerischer Landtag, 2021). Their persistence bore fruit: an amendment to the Road Traffic Act, a “paradigm shift” coming into force in October 2024, grants states and municipalities expanded powers over traffic planning (ARL, 2025). “In any case, the decisive requirement for effectively utilising the extended options is that the political will exists locally and that there is a willingness to endure possible conflicts and take legal risks” (ARL, 2025, p. 11; own translation). The issue remains polarising: while 45% of Bavarians support a citywide 30 kilometres/hour limit and bicycle access to all roads, more than half oppose it (SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH, 2023).

Inventing new rules: Co-creating new governance levels

Governance levels are not fixed but may be reconfigured or co-created through interaction between civil society and institutional actors. This includes the emergence of intermediate or cross-municipal spaces of coordination that do not correspond neatly to existing administrative

borders. This takes into account the fact that mobility does not stop at administrative borders and that collective identities do not necessarily coincide with specific municipalities, counties, et cetera.

One example is a region where several municipalities, confronted with shared topographical challenges and a common political discourse space, formed a joint ADFC chapter. This collaboration emerged from the realisation that isolated local initiatives lacked impact. By pooling resources and expertise, civil society actors, administrators, and local politicians created a quasi-regional structure for addressing cycling issues.

However, this informal level faces institutional constraints. For instance, the AGFK only accepts single municipalities or entire counties – not collective applications from intermediate governance levels (Interview 10: Municipal administration, 2023).

In another example, two neighbouring counties have developed close ties through a joint VCD chapter and coordinated local initiatives. Here, collective agency is not limited to civil society: political-administrative cooperation (e.g. in tourism) reinforces and legitimises this emergent governance space.

A third case illustrates how regional identity is strengthened through ADFC certification as a recognised bicycle tourism destination. While political and administrative stakeholders nominate the region, the ADFC federal association sets the criteria, offers technical guidance, and ultimately validates the new “bicycle travel region.” In this way, civil society helps to create, define, and institutionalise new governance spaces.

These three modes illustrate the flexibility and creativity with which civil society actors navigate, contest, and reshape the spatial and institutional architectures of governance. Whether working within existing frameworks, pushing to redefine them, or co-creating new ones, collective agency plays a central role in the unfolding conflict over bicycle mobility in Bavaria.

Conclusions

Key insights and strengths of the study

Spatial planning for a socio-ecological mobility transition is inherently conflictual, involving a diverse constellation of actors. Civil society has historically played a vital role in advancing sustainability transitions, and cycling activism is no exception. In Germany, grassroots cycling movements have surged in recent years, with over 50 municipal and state-level referenda launched since 2015. These initiatives strategically use direct democratic instruments – such as citizens' petitions and referenda – to advocate for improved cycling conditions

This article has argued that a spatial perspective is essential for a deeper understanding of civil society conflicts over the mobility transition, particularly in relation to navigating MLG

systems. Drawing on the CFA framework, the Embedded Agency Perspective, and MLG theory, we propose a robust conceptual framework for analysing spatially embedded conflicts across governance levels. This framework integrates multiple conflict dimensions – context, actors, dynamics, objects, and modes – with four spatial dimensions: physical, cultural, actor and agency, and regulative space, each situated across interrelated governance levels.

The case study of the conflict over cycling policy in Bavaria (2017–2023) illustrates the power of this analytical framework and aids a deeper understanding how spatial and governance dimensions are deeply intertwined across all conflict aspects: The *conflict context* is shaped by regulatory opportunities and constraints, particularly those governing civil society participation and direct democratic tools, which vary by governance level — highlighting the intersection of the regulative and actor and agency dimensions of space. The actor constellation reveals a complex division of competencies across political and administrative levels and the emergence of broad alliances between civil society and opposition parties — underscoring the importance of the *actor and agency dimension*. The *conflict dynamics* reveal temporal shifts in the dominant level of engagement, from local to state and partially to federal levels, reflecting how conflicts evolve spatially and institutionally over time. Regarding the *conflict object*, we showed that while most actors nominally support improved cycling conditions, substantive disagreements exist concerning how physical and regulatory spaces should be reorganised, particularly regarding road space allocation and legal responsibilities. Finally, we identified three *modes of conflict engagement* by civil society actors, illustrating how they interact with and reshape the governance system: 1. Playing by the rules: Civil society actors strategically align with the existing multi-level governance structure, addressing demands to responsible levels based on formal competencies. This requires extensive knowledge of governance systems, often acquired through processes of collective learning and supported by increasing professionalisation of civil society organisations. 2. Adjusting the rules: By challenging which decision-making powers belong to which levels, civil society actors can open up new entry points for intervention, forge cross-level and cross-sectoral alliances, and contribute to a broader democratisation of planning processes. 3. Inventing new rules: Through the co-creation of new governance spaces – such as inter-municipal collaborations or regionally coordinated initiatives – civil society actors (often in cooperation with political and administrative stakeholders) foster new collective identities and institutional arrangements, challenging the boundaries of traditional governance structures.

At its core, then, this conflict is in several respects about the question of governance levels and thus offers an opportunity for the reflection and reconfiguration of multi-level governance.

The following potential implications for various stakeholder groups in relation to multi-level governance can be derived from the analysis:

- *Civil society*: Development of a theory of change that specifically includes a multi-level strategy;
- *Politics*: Creation of greater clarity in the governance framework, better access opportunities for civil society at all levels of governance, and direct democratic instruments at federal level;
- *Administration*: Improvement of cooperation between the levels to avoid the ping-pong effect, support of civil society by acting as a pilot for the governance levels;
- *Academia*: Creation of spaces for conflict management and exchange between levels and actors; support in the clear articulation of conflicts between and across levels and in the identification of the various spatial dimensions affected.

These findings offer an important empirical and conceptual contribution to understanding how spatial conflicts unfold in planning processes – extending beyond the Bavarian case or even the mobility transition in Germany. They provide valuable insights for scholars and practitioners concerned with spatial governance, territorial development, and participatory planning, and underscore the central role of civil society in shaping socio-ecological transformations from below.

Research Limitations

Several limitations of this study should be acknowledged:

- A widely discussed limitation of case study research — and qualitative social science more broadly — is the issue of generalisability. This study is designed to offer analytical rather than statistical generalisations, developing conceptual insights through in-depth engagement with a single, illustrative case (Thomas, 2021).
- The research was conducted during and shortly after the active phase of the conflict. As a result, it does not offer a long-term perspective on the impacts of the Bavarian Cycling Law or the evolving role of civil society actors post-implementation.
- Although the study is grounded in rich empirical material, including interviews, documents, and press analysis, the constraints of the journal article format necessitate selectivity in data presentation. Some empirical nuance and complexity – central to case study methodology — is inevitably lost in this condensed format.

Direction for future research

Based on our findings, we see various promising areas for future research:

- Given the ongoing nature of the conflict, a longitudinal study would be valuable – especially to assess the implementation and political consequences of the Bavarian Cycling Law. Comparative insights could be drawn from similar cases, such as the Berlin Mobility Law (2018), where civil society actors like Changing Cities have monitored implementation and identified significant delays and policy reversals.
- A meta-analysis of comparable case studies across Europe could shed light on the broader dynamics of spatially embedded civil society conflicts in the context of mobility transitions. Such comparative work could help identify recurring patterns, governance challenges, and the role of civil society across different spatial, cultural, and political settings.
- Further research is needed on civil society resistance to mobility transitions — specifically, cases in which organised groups campaign against sustainability-oriented mobility measures. Understanding how such actors interact with pro-transition movements could enhance understanding of the political and spatial polarisation surrounding the socio-ecological transformation of mobility systems.
- We recognise that the proposed analytical approach is open to further advancement, based on its application to different contexts.

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The authors declare no conflict of interest regarding this article's research, authorship, or publication.

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